

Analysis of the strain field of box panels made of G-flute corrugated board during compression by 3D Digital Image Correlation

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SUMMARY

To preserve goods, it is crucial to understand how G-flute board packaging deforms when they are subjected to compression loading during carriage and storage. Here the displacement and strain fields of box panels are measured by a 3D Digital Image Correlation method. The influence of the geometry of boxes on their buckling behaviour is emphasised.

Keywords: Corrugated board, G flutes, Digital Image Stereo-Correlation, Buckling

Introduction

There is an increasing demand in G-flute corrugated boards (also called nano-flute corrugated boards), which tend to replace other lightweight packaging materials such as folding boards or plastics. Boxes have to withstand significant compression loading conditions during carriage and storage. In order to evaluate their structural performance, the box compression test is the most currently performed experiment. It consists in compressing an empty container between two parallel plates at a constant velocity. Usually it is observed that buckling phenomena are localized in the box panels, which bulge out during compression. At the maximum recorded compression force, the deformation localises around the box corners where creases appear and develop. This maximum force is defined as the quasi-static compression strength of the box. The prediction of such strength is the main topic of interest of past and current research works. Some authors strengthened their efforts to obtain a description of the buckling and post-buckling behaviour of individual board panels [1-3]. In parallel, the box compression behaviour of boxes was studied by Mc Kee *et al.* [4] and Urbanik [5], who defined semi-empirical formula to predict the box compression strength, as well as by Beldie *et al.* [6] and Biancolini *et al.* [7] by the finite element method (FEM). But comparisons of these models with experimental results remain rather scarce and limited.

Some full-field optical techniques for displacement or strain measurements were occasionally used in order to characterise the mechanical behaviour of papers or paperboards [2,8,9] subjected to various loading conditions. In particular, Allansson and Svard [2] used a Digital Speckle Photography technique to measure the out-of-plane displacement of a panel loaded in compression using a specially designed supporting frame. Despite its interest, this technique gave only access to rather limited information on the displacement field, *i.e.* a component of the displacement field. Thorpe and Choi [8] made an attempt to measure the strains on surfaces of box panels loaded in compression in the case of convex and concave buckling by

using a classical Digital Image Correlation technique. They showed that the in-plane shear strains are significant in the corner regions. However measurements were only performed in 2D so that the information they gained on the strain field was incomplete: *e.g.* the contribution of the gradients of the out-of-plane displacement to the strain components could not be assessed. This could be particularly inadequate when dealing with buckling problems.

During the last decade, the DIC techniques have been increasingly developed. It is now possible to measure the 3D displacement field and the surface strain field of any 3D object by the digital image stereo-correlation technique (DISC or 3D DIC) [10,11]. In this paper, the objective is to describe the full 3D displacement field of all panels of boxes during compression using this 3D DIC technique. This will permit to describe accurately their actual boundary conditions, as well as to calculate accurately their strain field during the box compression test. In the first section of this paper, technical aspects related to the box manufacturing, the compression test and the 3D imaging technique are given. Then, the evolution during compression of the displacement field on the surface of box panels is described. The influence of the box panel geometry is particularly investigated. Finally, the strain field is calculated and discussed.

Figure 1. (a) Picture of the cross-section of a G-flute profile corrugated board: image extracted from a 3D microtomography volume obtained at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) on beamline ID19. (b) Box blank. (c) Assembled box and dimensions.

G-flute corrugated board and box manufacturing

The material used in this study is a double-faced corrugated board with a G profile whose typical dimensions are shown in Fig. 1(a). This material has a nominal thickness e of 0.77 mm and an average basis weight of 450 g/m^2 . It is composed of a 160 g/m^2 kraftliner, a 110 g/m^2 corrugating medium and a 140 g/m^2 testliner. These papers are glued together using a starch-based adhesive.

Tested boxes have a square base. The box blanks were drawn using the software ArtiosCad 5.2. They were cut and creased in a Kongsberg XL22 cutting table. As shown in Fig. 1(b,c), the box blank includes panels, flaps, scores and a manufacturer joint. The crease depth was chosen equal to 1 mm. The box dimensions are referred by a for its height and b for its length and depth. Once the box was erected and glued, the inner and outer flaps covered completely the top and bottom box surfaces. Note that the flutes are vertical in the box panels: this means that the cross-direction of the corrugated board is aligned along the compression axis (see below).

Compression tests

Compression tests are performed with an Instron 5569 Press at a compression velocity of 13 mm/min along the \underline{e}_y direction; *cf.* Fig. 2(a). The compression plates are made up of polished aluminium. A photograph of a box, which is placed between the compression plates before the test, is shown in Fig. 2(a). During these experiments, the compression force F and the axial plate displacement Δa were on-line recorded. This permitted to calculate the following macroscopic box axial stress Σ simply defined as

$$\Sigma = \frac{F}{S_0}, \quad (1)$$

where $S_0 = 4e(b - e)$ is defined arbitrarily as the surface of the box cross-section perpendicular to the compression axis \underline{e}_z . Similarly, a macroscopic strain ε is defined as

$$\varepsilon = \ln\left(\frac{a + \Delta a}{a}\right). \quad (2)$$

A typical stress-strain curve obtained during a compression test is displayed in Fig. 2(b), as well as a deformed box in Fig. 2(c).

3D Digital Image Correlation technique

Two of the external panel surfaces were coated with a random pattern made of small black speckles. In order to estimate the 3D displacement field of these two surfaces, the 3D DIC technique was used. Here, this was performed with the DIC Software 7D [10]. During the compression test, two images of the deforming panels and of their superimposed speckle patterns are recorded simultaneously and sequentially by using, for stereovision, two CCD cameras (3872×2592 pixels, 25 Hz), whose relative position and orientation are known; *cf.* Fig. 2(d). Then, two image points belonging to a pair of simultaneously recorded images and corresponding to the same physical point of a panel are identified by applying a correlation-based stereo-matching technique. Briefly, the stereo-matching consists in finding the similarity or the correlation of a fixed window of 10×10 pixels, in our case, in the first image to a shifting window in the second image. Then, the 3D coordinates x' , y' and z' , of a physical point can be computed by triangulation. This permits to reconstruct the whole surface of the studied panels, as shown in Fig. 2(d). The 3D displacement field $\underline{\mathbf{u}}(x', y', z') = u'\underline{e}_{x'} + v'\underline{e}_{y'} + w'\underline{e}_{z'}$ of all points of the panels is measured by analysing a sequence of pair of stereo images using the image of the panels taken by the left camera in their initial configuration (before compression) as a reference. As an example, Fig. 2(e) shows the out-of-plane displacement w' of the surface of the two studied panels in the (x', y', z') coordinate system of the left camera. Finally, in this study, the displacement field was expressed in the panel local coordinate system (x, y, z) and smoothed by the Matlab[®] smooth

function along the x - and y -directions. In this latter coordinate system, the 3D displacement field is written as $\underline{\mathbf{u}}(x, y, z) = u\underline{\mathbf{e}}_x + v\underline{\mathbf{e}}_y + w\underline{\mathbf{e}}_z$. Fig. 2(f) displays the component w of this field for a panel with outer flaps.

Figure 2. (a) Picture of a box in the compression setup. (b) Typical experimental curve of the box compression stress with respect to the box compression strain. (c) Picture of the deformed box (final state). (d) Scheme of the imaging setup. (e) Reconstructed 3D images of the surfaces of panels before the compression test (initial state) and during the compression test at the maximum recorded stress (final state corresponding to point n°3 indicated in the graph 2(b)). (f) Component w' of the displacement field of the two studied panels in the (x', y', z') coordinate system. (g) Displacement w of the panel with outer flaps (see the arrow) in the panel coordinate system (x, y, z) .

Thereafter, the components E_{xx} , E_{yy} and E_{xy} of the Green-Lagrange strain tensor $\underline{\mathbf{E}}$ can be estimated for each panel:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{xx} &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 \right] \\
 E_{yy} &= \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right] \\
 2E_{xy} &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w}{\partial y}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

The above spatial partial derivatives are calculated by using a standard centred finite difference scheme.

Results: full displacement field of box panels

① $\varepsilon = 0.3\%$

② $\varepsilon = 1.7\%$

③ $\varepsilon = 3\%$

Figure 3. Maps of the components u , v and w of the displacement field at three compression stages noted 1, 2 and 3 corresponding to macroscopic compression strains $\varepsilon = 0.3\%$, 1.7% and 3% , respectively.

In this section, the above 3D DIC technique was used to describe the displacement field of two panels with inner and outer flaps of a cubic box with dimensions $73 \times 73 \times 73 \text{ mm}^3$ at three compression stages corresponding to macroscopic strains $\varepsilon = 0.3\%$, 1.7% and 3% , respectively. The corresponding stress-strain curve is that given in Fig. 2(b). As shown in this figure, the last compression strain $\varepsilon = 3\%$ corresponds to the box compression critical strain. The components u , v and w of the displacement field are displayed in Fig. 3 for the panel with outer flaps.

Firstly, it is worth noting that the displacement components are largely heterogeneous whatever the compression strain. The out-of-plane displacement w and the in-plane displacement v are of the same order and these two components are largely higher than the in-plane displacement u .

The out-of-plane displacement component w is never equal to zero, even for the first compression stage, *i.e.* $\varepsilon = 0.3\%$. This indicates clearly that the panel buckling is the predominant phenomenon and that it occurs and develops very early during the box compression. It is also interesting to notice that this field is not symmetric with respect to the horizontal median line of the panel. The maximum values of this component are obtained for a zone, located close to the top horizontal edge at the beginning of the compression, which is moved towards the bottom edge of the box at the critical strain, *i.e.* $\varepsilon = 3\%$. Besides, the surface of the zone was increased during the compression, as the values of w close to the box edges remained nearly equal to zero or were even slightly negative. Thus, high gradients for this component were found when going through the panel from its edges to the previous central zone, especially along the y -direction.

The component v of this displacement field was found to be of the same order as w . But quite astonishingly, it can also be observed that this component is nearly homogeneous over the whole panel surface. This means that the panel exhibits a vertical translatory motion during the box compression. Its origin might be related to a motion and a compression of the outer flaps joined to the panel, and more presumably to the crush of the junction scores during the compression experiment. Unfortunately, the scores are outside the correlation images. This point could be improved in future works.

The component u of the displacement field was observed to be small compared to v and w . It is nevertheless interesting to analyse it more precisely, especially for the last compression stage. It makes indeed appear that there are zones in the centre of the panel and close to its corners, where this component is very weak. On the contrary, along the vertical edges of the panel, this component is completely heterogeneous and shows a maximum approximately located at the median height of the panel. Thus, during the box compression, the vertical edges of the panel do not remain straight and tend to move towards the panel centre as the compression strain increases.

Fig. 4 permits to compare the behaviour of the panel with outer flaps and the panel with inner flaps. Their geometry can be compared in Fig. 4(a). The figures 4(b) and 4(c) give the change of Δv , defined as the positive difference between the vertical v displacements of the bottom and top horizontal edges, and w_{max} with respect to the compression stress Σ up to its critical value. The parameter Δv permits to assess the reduction of the height¹ of the correlation images of both studied panels during the compression test. The parameter w_{max} is the maximum recorded out-of-plane w displacement of both panels at the various compression stages. For both panels, the observed tendencies for these two graphs are quite similar. During

¹ This height is the same for both panels!

a first stage, these parameters exhibit a smooth increase with the increase of the stress, and finally a sudden increase. The transition between these two regions is related to the occurrence of localised deformation in the form of creases, which initiate from the panels' corners. This phenomenon is described in another paper [13].

Figure 4. (a) Pictures showing the difference of height between the panel with over flaps (panel A) and the panel with inner flaps (panel B). (b) Height reduction Δv versus box compression stress for both panels. (c) Maximum out-of-plane displacement w_{max} for both panels.

The main point given by these two graphs is the difference between the values of Δv and w_{max} obtained for the panel with inner flaps, which are systematically 30% or 40%, respectively,

lower than those of the panel with outer flaps. This reveals that the buckling phenomenon of panels is heterogeneous at the box scale. The origin of this different behaviour between both types of panels can be attributed to their differences of geometry. The panels with inner flaps is indeed a little bit shorter than the panel with outer flaps, and this implies for both panels small differences in their loading conditions and aspect ratios. Therefore, their buckling behaviour is different.

Figure 5. (a) Components of the Green-Lagrange strain tensor of the panel with outer flaps at the critical strain $\varepsilon = 3\%$. (b) Maps of the gradients of the in-plane displacement u and out-of-plane displacement w contributing to the strain component E_{xx} . (c) Same maps for the strain component E_{yy} .

Results: strain field of box panels

When calculating the components of the Green-Lagrange strain tensor (Eq. 3), it appeared that the contribution of some spatial gradients of u , v and w could be neglected. This permits to write the strain components E_{xx} , E_{yy} and $2E_{xy}$ adopting the following reduced expressions, which correspond to a von Kármán-type strain field:

$$\begin{aligned}
E_{xx} &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 \\
E_{yy} &= \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)^2 \\
2E_{xy} &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w}{\partial y}
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Figure 5(a) shows the components E_{xx} , E_{yy} and $2E_{xy}$ of the strain field at the critical compression strain $\varepsilon = 3\%$ for the panel with the outer flaps. Whatever these components, their values are almost equal to zero in the region of the panel centre. In contrast, along the panel edges the strain variations are more pronounced. The variations of E_{xx} are particularly important along the vertical edges of the box, whereas the variations of E_{yy} appear mainly along the horizontal edges of the panel. In both cases, these strain components have negative values, characteristic of a compressive deformation state. The maximum compressive strains are attained at the middle of the edges, and gradually decrease as the corner region is reached. It is also interesting to notice that the compressed zones along the x -axis are wider than along the y -axis, despite this direction corresponds to the box compression axis. The compressive strain E_{yy} is indeed more localised than the E_{xx} one. This corresponds to a complex strain situation, which might be related to a common influence of the phenomena of compression of the flaps and crush of the horizontal scores, as well as of the neighbouring panels.

Fig. 5(b,c) reveal the contributions of the gradient of the in-plane u and v displacements, and of the gradient of the out-of-plane w displacement to the strains E_{xx} and E_{yy} . This latter contribution has positive values, whereas the in-plane ones are negative. However, the out-of-plane contribution can only reach 50% at the maximum of the in-plane contribution. Of course, it cannot be neglected and emphasises the significant influence of the panel buckling on the strain state. But the in-plane contribution is predominant, and this explains why there are rather limited zones in tension at the surface of this panel despite its pronounced bulging due to the box compression.

Conclusion

A 3D DIC method was used and tailored to analyse the buckling behaviour of box panels during their compression. This technique is highly efficient to provide relevant and precious data on the 3D displacement and strain fields at the surface of the box panels. The analysis of the 3D displacement field provides information on the initiation and the development of the buckling behaviour of the studied panels. This permitted also to highlight the influence of scores and flaps on this phenomenon. It was shown that panels with outer or with inner flaps have a rather different behaviour during the box compression. It was assumed that this difference might arise from small differences in their geometry. The analysis of the strain field allowed distinguishing the relative contributions of the various displacement fields to the strain state of the panels. Compressive strain states are mainly found to be compressive along the box edges, whereas the central zone is nearly not loaded during the compression. This analysis provides data that can be used as input for post-buckling analytical or numerical models.

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